

THE STUDY OF CONSUMER SATISFACTION LEVEL WITH REFERENCE TO SERVICE ATTRIBUTES PROVIDED BY BIG BAZAAR

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Abstract:

In the era of globalisation, consumer satisfaction is extremely important to survive in the business world. The consumers needs, expectations, satisfaction level must be reviewed by the retailer on continuous basis.

With the changing retail environment, modern retail formats like hypermarkets are becoming very popular. Big Bazaar is the first such hypermarket in history of hypermarkets in India.

Product sold creates brand image for the manufacturer whereas services offered create reputation of the retailer.

The present paper aim at studying the expectations of consumers with regards to service attributes from hypermarkets.

Key Words:- Consumer satisfaction, services, Big Bazaar

Introduction:-

In a global economy, retailing plays an important role .It is one of the fastest growing industry in the world .

Consumer Satisfaction and Happiness and Positive approach from Consumer towards the business are Key elements of success in case of retailing business .

Many Big Business houses are entering into relating Future group is one of the such Company to enter into retailing .

From 1990 , the retail Sector in India has witnessed a very High level of transformation , Organised retail. Is India Started its development after 1990. Many with Future group many Big retail Companies started entering into market such as Reliance Fresh, Aadity Birla Group , Shopperes Shoppe, Subhiksha etc.

Big Bazaar is chain of shopping hubs in India Currently with more than 250. Retail outlets across the country. Big Bazaar is type of hypermarket; that service the need of entire family under one roof. The First store of Big Bazaar Started in October 2011. The Vision of Big Bazaar is to Emerge AS the Best and The Most Profitable Retailer in India.

The success of any Retail largely depends upon the types and quality of products offered . But the services provided by retail also has a key role in determining Satisfaction level of Consumer.

The Present Paper aims at Studing the expectations of Consumers from Big Bazaar Services provided by Big Bazaar .

Literature Review :-

Research Study by Kiran MC: - A Study of Customer service with reference to Big Bazaar, Banglore – (Visvesvraya Techonological University Belgaum) (July 2014) – This study is based on primary data and Secondary data. The Study mainly stresses on urban buying behaviour of the consumers. Same the main objectives of this study are to know the effectiveness of sales services provided by Big Bazaar; It also studies various customer service practices adopted by Big bazaar.

Research Methodology:-

This research paper is based on both Primary and Secondary data.

Primary data is collected from respondents who are the Consumers of Big Bazaar.

The Sample Size is 50

The secondary data has been taken from the available literature on organised retail and Big bazaar

Table 1 :-

Number of consumer

Male	23
Female	27
Total	50

Gender wise proportion of sample

Table 2 :-

Service Attributes of Big Bazaar	Number of respondent satisfied	Number of Respondents not satisfied	Total
Store Ambience is pleasant	34	16	50
Location of Big Bazaar	10	40	50
Parking Facility given by big Bazaar	40	10	50
Sales personnel in Big Bazaar	45	05	50
Efficiency of payment desk and waiting period	20	30	50
Asiles and Internal Design of stores	43	07	50
After sales services provided by Big Bazaar	10	40	50
Convineient time for shopping	46	04	50

Data Analysis :-

The above data reveal the following facts about Big Bazaar

Out of total 50 respondents 27 were male and remaining 23 were female . . Out of 27 male respondents 24 are satisfied with service provided by Big Bazaar. Whereas from female respondents out of 23, the number of respondent satisfied with Big Bazaar are 21.

The Stores ambience is Pleasant as per 68% of consumers. The majority consumers (80) % Feel that the should be more stores at different locations which will make their buying convenient.

According to 80% of the respondent the parking facilities provided by Big Bazaar are Sufficient. The data reveals that 90% of the Consumers are happy and satisfied with the sales personnel of Big Bazaar. These

sales personnel are efficiently assisting the consumer to make their shopping more enjoyable. The billing desk should improve its efficiency according to 60% of consumers' .Majority of these consumers referred about long que in front of billing desk especially in busy hours.

The internal design of Big Bazaar is very attractive and convenient. According to 86% of the respondents, they can get their required product in different brands and quantities very easily. The aisles are also wide to make the movement of consumers and shopping trolleys easily. People expect more about offer sales services. According to majority i.e 80% of the consumers were of the opinion that Big Bazaar do not provide any after sales services. The working hours of Big Bazaar are quiet long which makes the buying from Big Bazaar Convenient according to 92% of consumers.

Conclusion And Recommendations'

Conclusions

Big Bazaar is one of the leading hypermarket in India. It is successfully pulling more and more consumers. The study shows that Consumers are satisfied but have little more expectations. These expectations are given in the form of recommendations

Recommendations

1. Most of the consumers are happy and satisfied with the services provided by Big Bazaar. But efforts are required to study the areas where consumers have more expectations
2. There are certain areas of services, which needs more Concentration from Big Bazaar, such as after sale services or billing desk .
3. The Big Bazaar should open more locations for the Convenience of consumers.

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